

Supplement

Short halt in vaping modifies cardio-respiratory parameters and urine metabolome: a randomized trial

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*Martin Chaumont and Vanessa Tagliatti made equal contributions to this study

Running head: vaping cessation and cardiorespiratory function

Authors' contribution: MC and PVDB conceived the idea and design of the study. MC has full access to all of the study data and takes responsibility of the integrity and the accuracy of the data analysis. VT and JMC performed urine metabolomics analyses and drafted the methods for these analyses. EMC enrolled the participants. MC randomized the participants (sequence generation, allocation concealment, and intervention administration). EMC, SF recorded the outcome measurements. AB performed lung injury biomarkers analysis. GD performed serum nicotine and propylene glycol analyses. AVM performed the statistical analysis. TS and VF performed lung function tests. MC drafted the manuscript. VT, EMC, JMC, AB, SM, GD, AVM, ND, TS, VF and PVDB critically revised the manuscript for important intellectual content. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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Data availability statement:

1. Will individual participant data be available (including data dictionaries)?
 - Yes
2. What data in particular will be shared?
 - All of the individual participant data collected during the trial, after deidentification.
3. What other documents will be available?
 - Study protocol and statistical analysis plan
4. When and for how long the data will become/be available?
 - Immediately following publication. No end date.
5. The criteria to access the data (including who can request access and for what types of analyses, and the name of the data repository)?
 - For what types of analyses? Any purpose
 - Proposals should be directed to martin.chaumont@ulb.ac.be

As mentioned in the methods: Informed consent was obtained from all study participants after they received complete information regarding the study design. The latter was approved by the local Ethics Committee (Hôpital Erasme - CCB: B406201629930) and conformed to the Declaration of Helsinki. The study was registered at ClinicalTrials.gov (January 25, 2018), identifier NCT03410511. The full trial protocol can be accessed at <https://clinicaltrials.gov/ct2/show/NCT03410511>

The authors certify that (a) the material is original, has not been published, and is not being considered for publication elsewhere, including publicly accessible websites or e-print servers, (b) no part of the research presented has been funded by tobacco industry sources, and (c) all authors have read the manuscript and approve its submission.

Figure S1. Patient flow diagram (CONSORT - Consolidated Standards of Reporting Trials).

Figure S2. Representative 500 MHz ^1H -NMR baseline urine spectra from the nicotine-session (A); the nicotine-free-session (B) and the stop-session (C) in the same subject. 3-Hydroxyisoval: 3 – Hydroxyisovalerate; ACh: acetylcholine; Bet: betaine; DMA: dimethylamine; Hipp: hippurate; Methylhist: π -Methylhistidine; N-PAG: N-phenylacetyl glycine; PG: propylene glycol; Pyr: pyruvate; TMAO: trimethylamine oxide.

Table S.1.1. missing data in the nicotine-session		
	Data	Reasons for missing data
Nicotine-session (n = 26)		Four participants did not perform the nicotine session
SpO₂		
Baseline vs post-exposure (n - %)	26 (100%)	No missing data
TcpO₂/CO₂		
Baseline vs post-exposure (n - %)	26 (100%)	No missing data
EtCO₂		
Baseline vs post-exposure (n - %)	26 (100%)	No missing data
RR		
Baseline vs post-exposure (n - %)	26 (100%)	No missing data
SkBF		
Baseline vs post-exposure (n - %)	26 (100%)	No missing data
CVC		
Baseline vs post-exposure (n - %)	26 (100%)	No missing data
SBP		
Baseline vs post-exposure (n - %)	26 (100%)	No missing data
DBP		
Baseline vs post-exposure (n - %)	26 (100%)	No missing data
HR		
Baseline vs post-exposure (n - %)	26 (100%)	No missing data
Lung function test		
Post-exposure (n - %)	26 (100%)	No missing data
Diffusing capacity		
Post-exposure (n - %)	23 (88%)	Technical failure (n=1); quality criteria not reached (n=2)
Serum CC16		
Baseline vs post-exposure (n - %)	26 (100%)	No missing data
Urine CC16		
Baseline vs End (n - %)	26 (100%)	No missing data
Serum SP-D		
Baseline vs post-exposure (n - %)	26 (100%)	No missing data
Serum PG (LC-MS)		
Baseline (n - %)	21 (81%)	Our laboratory stopped this analysis from September 2018 (n=5)
Serum PG and other metabolites (1-H-RMN)		
Baseline (n - %)	24 (92%)	Technical failure (n=2)
Urine PG and other metabolites (1-H-RMN)		
Baseline (n - %)	25 (96%)	Technical failure (n=1)
Serum nicotine		
Baseline (n - %)	26 (100%)	No missing data

SpO₂, pulse oximetry; TcpO₂/CO₂, transcutaneous oxygen/carbon dioxide tensions; EtCO₂, end-tidal carbon dioxide; RR, respiratory rhythm; SkBF, skin microcirculatory blood flow; CVC, continuous vascular conductance; SBP, systolic blood pressure; DBP, diastolic blood pressure; HR, heart rate; CC16, club cell protein-16; SP-D, surfactant protein-D; PG, propylene glycol; LC-MS, liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry; 1-H-RMN, nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy

Table S.1.2. missing data in the nicotine-free-session		
	Data	Reasons for missing data
Nicotine-free-session (n = 28)		Two participants did not perform the nicotine free session
SpO₂		
Baseline vs post-exposure (n - %)	28 (100%)	No missing data
TcpO₂/CO₂		
Baseline vs post-exposure (n - %)	28 (100%)	No missing data
EtCO₂		
Baseline vs post-exposure (n - %)	28 (100%)	No missing data
RR		
Baseline vs post-exposure (n - %)	28 (100%)	No missing data
SkBF		
Baseline vs post-exposure (n - %)	28 (100%)	No missing data
CVC		
Baseline vs post-exposure (n - %)	27 (96%)	Beatscope data failure for technical reason (n=1)
SBP		
Baseline vs post-exposure (n - %)	27 (96%)	Beatscope data failure for technical reason (n=1)
DBP		
Baseline vs post-exposure (n - %)	27 (96%)	Beatscope data failure for technical reason (n=1)
HR		
Baseline vs post-exposure (n - %)	27 (96%)	Beatscope data failure for technical reason (n=1)
Lung function test		
Post-exposure (n - %)	28 (100%)	No missing data
Diffusing capacity		
Post-exposure (n - %)	28 (100%)	No missing data
Serum CC16		
Baseline vs post-exposure (n - %)	25 (89%)	Satisfactory vein puncture not achieved (n=3)
Urine CC16		
Baseline vs End (n - %)	25 (89%)	Failure for technical reason (n=3)
Serum SP-D		
Baseline vs post-exposure (n - %)	25 (89%)	Satisfactory vein puncture not achieved (n=3)
Serum PG (LC-MS)		
Baseline (n - %)	20 (71%)	Our laboratory stopped this analysis from September 2018 (n=8)
Serum PG and other metabolites (1-H-RMN)		
Baseline (n - %)	26 (93%)	Technical failure (n=2)
Urine PG and other metabolites (1-H-RMN)		
Baseline (n - %)	28 (100%)	No missing data
Serum nicotine		
Baseline (n - %)	27 (96%)	Satisfactory vein puncture not achieved (n=1)

SpO₂, pulse oximetry; TcpO₂/CO₂, transcutaneous oxygen/carbon dioxide tensions; EtCO₂, end-tidal carbon dioxide; RR, respiratory rhythm; SkBF, skin microcirculatory blood flow; CVC, continuous vascular conductance; SBP, systolic blood pressure; DBP, diastolic blood pressure; HR, heart rate; CC16, club cell protein-16; SP-D, surfactant protein-D; PG, propylene glycol; LC-MS, liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry; 1-H-RMN, nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy

Table S.1.3. missing data in the stop-session		
	Data	Reasons for missing data
Stop-session (n = 22)		Height participants did not perform the stop session
SpO₂		
Baseline vs post-exposure (n - %)	22 (100%)	No missing data
TcpO₂/CO₂		
Baseline vs post-exposure (n - %)	22 (100%)	No missing data
EtCO₂		
Baseline vs post-exposure (n - %)	22 (100%)	No missing data
RR		
Baseline vs post-exposure (n - %)	22 (100%)	No missing data
SKBF		
Baseline vs post-exposure (n - %)	22 (100%)	No missing data
CVC		
Baseline vs post-exposure (n - %)	22 (100%)	No missing data
SBP		
Baseline vs post-exposure (n - %)	22 (100%)	No missing data
DBP		
Baseline vs post-exposure (n - %)	22 (100%)	No missing data
HR		
Baseline vs post-exposure (n - %)	22 (100%)	No missing data
Lung function test		
Post-exposure (n - %)	22 (100%)	No missing data
Diffusing capacity		
Post-exposure (n - %)	22 (100%)	No missing data
Serum CC16		
Baseline vs post-exposure (n - %)	22 (100%)	No missing data
Urine CC16		
Baseline vs End (n - %)	22 (100%)	No missing data
Serum SP-D		
Baseline vs post-exposure (n - %)	22 (100%)	No missing data
Serum PG (LC-MS)		
Baseline (n - %)	18 (82%)	Our laboratory stopped this analysis September 2018 (n=4)
Serum PG and other metabolites (1-H-RMN)		
Baseline (n - %)	22 (100%)	No missing data
Urine PG and other metabolites (1-H-RMN)		
Baseline (n - %)	22 (100%)	No missing data
Serum nicotine		
Baseline (n - %)	22 (100%)	No missing data

SpO₂, pulse oximetry; TcpO₂/CO₂, transcutaneous oxygen/carbon dioxide tensions; EtCO₂, end-tidal carbon dioxide; RR, respiratory rhythm; SKBF, skin microcirculatory blood flow; CVC, continuous vascular conductance; SBP, systolic blood pressure; DBP, diastolic blood pressure; HR, heart rate; CC16, club cell protein-16; SP-D, surfactant protein-D; PG, propylene glycol; LC-MS, liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry; 1-H-RMN, nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy